

Matrix of Digital Literacy learning objectives in the Humanities Bachelor degrees

Within the Faculty of Humanities, it has been decided to define digital literacy in the bachelor programmes' Education and Examination Regulations (EER) by means of an intended learning outcome. The route to attaining this outcome has been discussed with the Board of Education Directors on multiple occasions. In these discussions, the matrix below was applied in various ways: as a proposed route, as a tool to map existing activities in the degree programmes, and as a collection of suggestions on how to organize education. Degree programmes are *not* asked to commit to the entire matrix: interpretation of the learning trajectory is, to an extent, programme-specific according to the needs of the discipline.

Intended learning outcome

"The student has the skill to responsibly and critically collect, manage, evaluate and analyze digital sources and data, and is aware of relevant societal influences and implications of digitization within their own field of study."

Legend

- Yellow: basic learning objectives
- Green: in-depth learning objectives
- Blue: additional learning objectives

Matrix

0. Expected entry level

ID	LEARNING OBJECTIVE	PRACTICAL IMPLEMENTATION	EXAMPLES	NOTES
0.1	Can manage their own computer.	<i>-The student has basic skills needed to use their own computer sustainably and effectively.</i>	Making back-ups; downloading and installing software and updates; applying functional folder structures; applying functional file names.	Is able to understand and resolve computer notifications. <i>-This is an entry requirement to all degree programmes, so it is neither taught nor assessed within the programmes.</i>

				-The University Library provides a module in period 1 and period 3 for first-year students apparently lacking these basic skills (by analogy with the Skills Lab).
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1. searching and selecting: sources and heuristics

ID	LEARNING OBJECTIVE	PRACTICAL IMPLEMENTATION	EXAMPLES	NOTES
1.1	Has knowledge of some relevant (online) source collections.	<p><i>-The student is aware of those collections which are important for the degree programme.</i></p> <p><i>-The student is able to locate these collections.</i></p> <p><i>-The student is familiar with repositories relevant to the programme (i.e. depot and search engine for collections) to find collections.</i></p>	Gutenberg, DBNL, Delpher, Beeld & Geluid, Corpus Gesproken Nederlands, The Guardian, The Internet Archive, University Library Special Collections, LitLab, Childes, reviews, etc.	selection by field and/or degree programme
1.2	Has knowledge of and can work with relevant search engines.	<p><i>-The student is able to work with the search engines chosen by the degree programme.</i></p> <p><i>-The student is able to independently locate sources within collections.</i></p>	Google, WorldCat, Google Scholar	See also University Library LibGuides and library instructions

		<p><i>-The student is able to annotate the sources, and manage these annotations systematically.</i></p> <p><i>-The student is able to work with Boolean operators (AND, OR, NOT, etc.).</i></p>		
1.3	Can reflect on role of search engines in heuristics.	<p><i>-The student is familiar with basic principles of Text Search and Image Search.</i></p> <p><i>-The student has knowledge of the role of metadata in search engines.</i></p> <p><i>-The student has knowledge of the role of algorithms in search engines.</i></p>		Note that language students must also be able to search for and find in own source language (besides Dutch and English, also Spanish, German, French, Italian, Celtic languages, Arabic, Turkish).
1.4	Can critically evaluate sources and materials that were found, taking into account collection, search engines and own search strategy.	<p><i>-The student is able to perform source criticism on digital sources (both digital born and digitized sources).</i></p> <p><i>-The student has knowledge of different search strategies and search engines tailored to said strategies, such as targeted search (focused on one specific source), and exploratory search (focused on exploring the collection, in which serendipity plays a large part).</i></p>	taking into account input errors (OCR, ASR); who compiled the collection and with which goal; what <i>is</i> and what is <i>not</i> part of the collection, and why; what are the licensing conditions; etc.	Taking into account source language (see above) and situatedness of collection.

		<i>-The student has been introduced to the situatedness of metadata.</i>		
1.5	Can critically evaluate metadata of sources and materials, taking into account collection, search engines and own search strategy.	<p><i>-The student has knowledge of and can reflect on metadata generated by OCR (optical character recognition).</i></p> <p><i>-The student has knowledge of and can reflect on metadata generated by ASR (automated speech recognition).</i></p> <p><i>-The student has knowledge of and can reflect on metadata generated by image recognition.</i></p> <p><i>-The student can reflect on the situatedness of metadata.</i></p>		
1.6	Can collect data independently, taking into account standards and conventions of the field of study.	<p><i>-The student is able to download digital data and store it in line with the applicable agreements.</i></p> <p><i>-The student has knowledge of the principles of data scraping.</i></p> <p><i>-The student has knowledge of the ethical conventions related to collecting data from digital sources.</i></p>		

1.7	Can independently collect digital data from online sources on a large scale, taking into account standards and conventions of the field of study.	<i>-The student is able to 'scrape' digital data in line with the applicable agreements.</i>		
1.8	Can efficiently manage their own bibliographic data.	<i>-Student is aware of different bibliographic management systems.</i> <i>-Student is able to manage a bibliographic management system.</i>	Zotero, RefWorks	
1.9	Can manage data they collected.	<i>-The student can manage their own digital data in a data management system.</i>	Taking into account GDPR legislation and RDM prerequisites.	See checklist for students on GDPR, privacy and ethics: https://students.uu.nl/sites/default/files/Student%20checklist%20-%20human-subject%20related%20research-FETC.pdf
1.10	Has knowledge of the Open Data principles.	<i>- The student has basic knowledge of the FAIR data principles.</i> <i>-The student has basic knowledge of copyright.</i> <i>-The student has basic knowledge of distribution rights (Creative Commons licensing, Fair Use or other internationally recognized distribution agreements and licenses).</i>		

1.11	Is familiar with principles of open science/scholarship.	<p><i>-The student can apply the FAIR principles as analytical instrumentation.</i></p> <p><i>-The student is familiar with the academic reasoning behind Open Access.</i></p> <p><i>-The student is familiar with the degrees of Open Access.</i></p> <p><i>-The student is familiar with the UU repositories.</i></p>		<p>See also, among others:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://www.uu.nl/en/research/research-data-management/guides/how-to-make-your-data-fair • https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/ • https://www.uu.nl/en/research/open-science/tracks/open-access • https://www.uu.nl/en/university-library/advice-support-to/researchers/publishing-support/open-access • https://www.uu.nl/en/research/research-data-management/tools-services/tools-for-storing-and-managing-data/data-repository-finder

2. analyzing (in years BA1 and BA2)

ID	LEARNING OBJECTIVE	PRACTICAL IMPLEMENTATION	EXAMPLES	NOTES
2.1	Has been introduced to some relevant digital methods and tools for analyzing sources.	<i>-The student is aware of the existence of digital analysis methods for sources relevant to their field of study, thanks to examples or assignments.</i>		
2.2	Has basic skills in the use of some relevant digital methods and/or tools for analyzing sources.	<i>- The student has gained practical experience with one or more digital analysis methods for sources relevant to their field of study.</i>	Praat, Gephi, JASP, R packages, ELAN, Clariah Media Suite, Nvivo, Ngram viewer, AntConc, Voyant, I-Analyzer, GIS, Cinematics, DMI-tools, etc.	selection per field and/or degree programme; preferably open-source (to prevent vendor lock-in)
2.3	Has basic skills in cleaning up source material, including critical reflection on this.	<i>-The student is aware of the necessity of cleaning up data for the purpose of digital analysis.</i> <i>-The student possesses practical experience with and knowledge of data cleaning techniques (including selection, conversion).</i> <i>-The student is capable of reflecting critically on the consequences of clean-up and selection processes for the data's representativeness.</i>	OpenRefine; diligent file management;	

2.4	Can derive abstract patterns from digital sources, and evaluate these.	<p><i>-The student is capable of interpreting the output of digital analysis based on substantive knowledge.</i></p> <p><i>-The student has basic knowledge of descriptive statistics (e.g. is able to convert absolute values to relative values) for the purpose of evaluation of analyses.</i></p>		
2.5	Can critically evaluate tools.	<p><i>-The student has knowledge of concepts, questions and techniques to critically evaluate digital methods and tools. (E.g. Who designed the tool? For whom is the tool designed? Which restrictions does the tool have for data analysis? To what degree is the tool transparent/a black box?)</i></p>		

3. presenting, publishing, and disseminating

ID	LEARNING OBJECTIVE	PRACTICAL IMPLEMENTATION	EXAMPLES	NOTES
3.1	Can justify choices in research process clearly.	<p><i>- The student is capable of making reasoned choices in presentation formats based on research question and source materials.</i></p>		Regarding searching for sources, selecting, annotating, analyzing: this is part of the intended learning outcome, too.

3.2	Has knowledge of principles of reusing materials in their own publications.	<p>- <i>The student is aware of the applicable rules regarding reuse (GDPR, copyright, portrait rights).</i></p> <p>- <i>The student has knowledge of the principles regarding correct use of others' materials in their own work (acknowledgement), including multimedia sources such as Open Images (which may be used freely) and images and videos protected by copyright, for which strict rules apply.</i></p>		
3.3	Has basic knowledge of and skills in visualizing key patterns within sources.	- <i>The student has knowledge of techniques to visualize source materials relevant to the field of study.</i>	network, cluster diagram; word clouds per topic; scattergram;	Selection by domain/degree programme.
3.4	Is familiar with digital reporting of research results.	- <i>The student is familiar with various digital presentation formats (data stories, vlog, blog, digital poster, website, podcast, video essay, etc.)</i>		
3.5	Can critically evaluate various forms of digital reporting of research results.	- <i>The student can reflect critically on the digital presentation format, as well as on the impact of presentation format and content.</i>		
3.6	Can create digital reports of research results.	- <i>The student has the skills to present research results digitally in a format relevant to the field of study.</i>		Disseminating their own work through online channels is explicitly not a part of the intended learning objectives: BA

				students are still learning, and as such their BA products should not be published online.
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4. societal influences and consequences

ID	LEARNING OBJECTIVE	PRACTICAL IMPLEMENTATION	EXAMPLES	NOTES
4.1	Can reflect on societal and ethical consequences of the digital society for own field of study.	<p><i>-The student can form an opinion on the selective availability of digital data.</i></p> <p><i>-The student can form an opinion on the economic and social consequences of digital platforms.</i></p> <p><i>-The student can reflect on growing datafication and the consequences of this on today's society.</i></p> <p><i>-The student is aware of the conflict between growing (digital) surveillance and guarding our privacy.</i></p> <p><i>-The student is aware of the steering effect of algorithms.</i></p>	Individual freedom of choice vs large-scale trends; filter bubbles and fake news; bias vs diversity; ethical aspects (Dutch childcare benefits scandal)	

5. learning and developing

ID	LEARNING OBJECTIVE	PRACTICAL IMPLEMENTATION	EXAMPLES	NOTES
5.1	Has sufficient learning skills to enhance and expand digital literacy and competences.	<i>-The student acknowledges which skills are lacking and knows where additional skills can be acquired.</i>	cdh.uu.nl/ ; Library DH Support	For course offerings, see cdh.uu.nl/education and relevant minors (Artificial Intelligence, Applied Data Science); see also www.programminghistorian.org , www.github.com ; selection per field of study/degree programme

6. Extra: specific learning objectives

ID	LEARNING OBJECTIVE	PRACTICAL IMPLEMENTATION	EXAMPLES	NOTES
6.1	Has insight and skill in quantitative methods and statistics, at an introductory level.	<i>-The student has followed an introductory module on quantitative methods and statistics.</i> <i>-The student can apply statistical analyses in their own research.</i>		e.g. course Methods and Statistics 1 (TW2V19002)
6.2	Has insight and skill in programming, at an introductory level.	<i>-The student has become proficient in either R or Python through modules or tutorials.</i>		e.g. course Programming with Python (BETA-B1PYT)
6.3	Can process text in Markdown or LaTeX.	<i>-The student knows the distinction between Markdown and LaTeX for authors and readers.</i>		Instead of MS Word (and without WYSIWYG)

		<i>-The student can write simple texts using Markdown or LaTeX.</i>		
6.4	Can work with Jupyter Notebook and/or R Markdown.	<i>-The student is familiar with the principles of the Jupyter Community.</i> <i>-The student has sufficient knowledge of Python or R to work with Jupyter Notebook.</i> <i>-The student has sufficient knowledge of R to work with Markdown.</i>		For the purpose of “data stories” like https://labs.kadaster.nl/stories/digitaal-erfgoed/
6.5	Is familiar with query languages.	<i>-The student is familiar with the specificity of various query languages.</i> <i>-The student has experience running queries using SPARQL, SQL, Linked Open Data.</i>		

In an earlier phase, contributions to this matrix in the original (Dutch) language were given by Hugo Quené, Pim Huijnen, Jasmijn van Gorp, Karin van Es, Dominik Klein, Manuela Pinto, Jeroen Salman, André van Kooij, Iris Mulders.